

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new RIs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
PROJECT TITLE	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
PROJECT ACRONYM	H2IOSC
PROJECT ID	IR0000029
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it
CUP	B63C22000730005
WP	4
OU	OU1 Istituto Opera del Vocabolario - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	4.14
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Common semantic framework (final)
EXPECTED DELIVERY DATE	30.4.2024
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	31.08.2025
<p>This project is funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them</p>	

Authors

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CNR-OVI	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	emiliano.deglinnocenti@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Francesco Coradeschi	francesco.coradeschi@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Francesco Pinna	francesco.pinna@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Alessia Spadi	alessia.spadi@cnr.it

ABSTRACT:

WP4 is focused on developing interoperability between available resources both at a physical level, creating the H2IOSC National Cloud Infrastructure and at a semantic level, by translating the state of knowledge with respect to the resources offered by each RI into a common semantic interdisciplinary and interoperable representation.

WP4 focuses on the alignment (i.e.: collection, cleaning, mapping, and modeling) of resources gathered by the 4 participating RIs. To facilitate the alignment, a common mapping schema has been deployed to support the data transformation process: from the original format(s) towards the H2IOSC reference specifications.

The development of H2IOSC's Common Semantic Framework, which comprises the set of all specifications, is meant to create a level of interoperability between resources gathered by RIs, by providing a shared conceptual reference model to represent information coming from heterogeneous sources using a common vision.

The development workflow involved: i) analyzing the state of the art and focusing on common problems related to the management of information provided by the RIs; ii) providing a pipeline of validated actions and guidelines on the assessment and semantization of data; iii) offering practical methods for heterogeneous data integration, including transformation and validation, fostering resources exploitation and reuse. Those actions resulted in the development of a coherent method for the validation, sharing and interoperability of resources provided by the RIs, which will be kept continuously updated to ensure the alignment of the H2IOSC infrastructure with FAIR principles.

<u>LIST OF ACRONYMS</u>	<u>4</u>
<u>INTRODUCTION</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>1. COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK.....</u>	<u>7</u>
1.1 WHAT IS A COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK?	7
1.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS.....	7
<u>2. SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS IN PREVIOUS PROJECTS</u>	<u>8</u>
2.1 CENDARI	8
2.2 PARTHENOS	10
2.3 SSHOC.....	12
<u>3. INTERRELATION WITH OTHER WPS</u>	<u>14</u>
<u>4. THE COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK IN H2IOSC.....</u>	<u>14</u>
4.1 LIST OF DATATYPES.....	15
4.2 ARCHITECTURAL MAPPING	15
4.3 DATA/INTEGRATION MODEL.....	16
4.4 MAINTENANCE AND CONSTANT UPDATING.....	17
4.5 FEDERATION PILOT: APPLIED INTEROPERABILITY STRATEGIES IN WP4	18
4.6 DOMAIN-SPECIFIC ONTOLOGIES.....	18
4.7 ONTOLOGICAL DECISION AND H2IOSC-CSF PROFILE	18
<u>5. CONCLUSIONS.....</u>	<u>19</u>
<u>6. FINAL RELEASE OF D4.14 AND STRATEGY FOR CONSTANT UPDATING</u>	<u>20</u>
<u>REFERENCES</u>	<u>21</u>

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CC	Creative Commons
CC-BY / CC0	Creative Commons Attribution / Public Domain Dedication
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN-IT	Italian national node of Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN-ERIC)
CSV / TSV / CSV-W	Comma-Separated Values / Tab-Separated Values / CSV on the Web
DARIAH-IT	Italian national node of Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH-ERIC)
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Vocabulary Application Profile
DOCX	Microsoft Word Open XML Document
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EAC-CPF	Encoded Archival Context – Corporate Bodies, Persons, and Families
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
E-RIHS.it	Italian national node of the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FOAF	Friend of a Friend Ontology
GLTF	GL Transmission Format (3D model exchange format)
H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes (BIM format)
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework

ISAAR	International Standard Archival Authority Record
ISAD	International Standard Archival Description
JSON / JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation / JSON for Linked Data
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MARC21 / UNIMARC	Machine-Readable Cataloging formats for bibliographic data
OA	Open Annotation
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OPERAS-IT	Italian national node of Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities (OPERAS)
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RVT	Autodesk Revit Project format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology (W3C Recommendation)
RFC	Request for Comments
RI	Research Infrastructure
S&CI	Social and Cultural Innovation
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud Reference Ontology
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative

INTRODUCTION

The H2IOSC (Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) project aims at establishing a federated and inclusive cluster of European Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the ESFRI domain of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) based on the Italian nodes of CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHIS, and OPERAS. Focused on fostering collaboration among researchers in humanities, language technologies, and cultural heritage, the initiative aims to facilitate the sharing of tools, services, and data.

The main objective of the project is the creation of a national infrastructure for the Humanities and Heritage Sciences in Italy, consolidating the existing national nodes of the participating RIs. Through this integration, H2IOSC endeavors to provide a comprehensive and collaborative platform, enhancing research capabilities and cross-disciplinary cooperation in the specified domains.

The main goal of Work Package 4 (**RIs Nodes and Resources Interoperability**), is to establish a unified approach for managing humanities and cultural heritage materials, addressing familiar challenges arising from the use of multiple digital platforms, tools, and standards:

- High degree of data fragmentation;
- Limited information retrieval;
- Low Integration, isolated contexts;
- Data Overload;
- Limited Accessibility;
- Technological obsolescence;
- Lack of interoperability between systems;
- Data lock-in.

WP4 has two primary focuses to achieve interoperability: i) the construction of the physical infrastructure (i.e. the network of data centers), and ii) the implementation of a common semantic framework to promote the FAIRness of the shared data, tools, and other resources.

The specific focus is on achieving semantic interoperability, context preservation, and accessibility of contents beyond their original context. WP4 aims to integrate tools for the management of thesauri and vocabularies, ensuring consistent handling of resources within the same environment.

This deliverable represents the culmination of the work described in D4.1 (Definition for data, services, software platform policy implementation) and further developed in D4.13 (Common semantic framework (interim)). Building on the conceptual and methodological foundation laid in these earlier deliverables, D4.14 provides the final implementation model of the Common Semantic Framework (referred to as **CSF** from here on), which integrates the principles of interoperability, semantic alignment, and sustainability into the H2IOSC ecosystem. To maintain the readability and usability of the document, it was decided (where relevant) not to omit certain sections, even though they are already included in section 4.13.

The CSF is designed to ensure that data, services, and tools from the participating RIs can be semantically mapped, interconnected, and accessed in a harmonized way.

Through this framework, H2IOSC ensures that heterogeneous datasets can be interoperable, accessible through the Marketplace, reusable across RIs, tools and platforms, and semantically connected to the broader EOSC and SSHOC ecosystems.

This deliverable therefore marks the transition from theoretical design to full operationalization of the semantic layer, establishing a sustainable, extensible, and community-driven model for the semantic interoperability of Humanities and Heritage Science data.

1. COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK

1.1 WHAT IS A COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK?

In the context of the H2IOSC project, leveraging the experience of previous endeavors such as CENDARI¹, PARTHENOS², and SSHOC³, the *Common Semantic Framework* is defined as a set of standards, definitions and workflows allowing information storage and retrieval from multiple, heterogeneous data sources. This framework can be described in terms of two primary sets of processes:

- A pipeline of validated actions and guidelines for the assessment and semantization of data.
- A practical workflow, including a fully working implementation, for the homogenization of data, their transformation (to the defined semantic model) and their validation.

In practice, the framework should provide a robust and scalable data management infrastructure, allowing efficient and accurate information acquisition, processing and storage, and facilitating information retrieval. Given the vast amount of data potentially available, originating from diverse sources and in various formats, having a standardized methodology for effective data handling is a fundamental requirement for the H2IOSC project; the heterogeneity of data in terms of both format and structure means that standardization is a significant challenge. It is important to stress that the semantic framework does not seek to replace source data, but to integrate them in a shared environment with the aim of improving the degree of FAIRness of the various resources.

1.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS

The definition and structure of the CSF, presented in deliverable D4.13, represented a key milestone in the development of H2IOSC's semantic interoperability model. Since then, the framework has been significantly refined and strengthened through the work documented in D4.1 - Definition for data, services, software platform policy implementation, which provided a comprehensive vision for the semantic governance of data, tools, and services across the federated infrastructure. D4.1 contributed essential conceptual and operational guidelines regarding data typologies, standardization policies, metadata handling, and the alignment of semantic layers with the Marketplace architecture.

In addition, intermediate outputs from D4.8, D4.9, D4.10, and D4.13 itself have collectively contributed to the construction of a consistent and reusable semantic backbone. These deliverables helped test, evaluate, and validate the key components of the CSF, such as controlled vocabularies, metadata crosswalks, and mapping tools.

Thanks to these iterative contributions, H2IOSC has now reached an advanced phase of semantic framework consolidation, moving from design to operational readiness. The current version of the CSF presented in D4.14 reflects a mature and implementable model, capable of supporting cross-RI interoperability, semantic alignment of resources, and FAIR data practices within the infrastructure. This final deliverable marks a transition to the full implementation and governance phase, laying out the foundation for sustainable integration across platforms and domains.

In the critical and highly non-trivial task of constructing the framework, the H2IOSC project was able to leverage valuable know-how gathered from multiple federated Research Infrastructures (RIs) in

¹ Cfr.: <http://www.cendari.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

² Cfr.: <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

³ Cfr.: <https://sshopencloud.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

prior projects. In this section, we will examine the solutions adopted in past experiences in the context of Social Sciences and Humanities, including the already mentioned CENDARI, PARTHENOS, and SSHOC projects. Each of these projects has significantly contributed to data management practices, providing detailed workflows that serve as an excellent foundation for our current activities.

The fundamental elements to build a solid common semantic framework, derived from previous experiences, are:

- A set of strict definitions capable of describing all collected data through a unified language
- Standardized vocabularies, taxonomies and/or ontologies supporting the standard definitions
- A practical and articulated data integration workflow, to convert input data to the shared ontology, store them, and make them accessible

To have an effective semantic framework, the domain experts' contribution is essential, especially in the process of data collection and validation.

2. SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS IN PREVIOUS PROJECTS

We will now examine in more detail the data integration and homogenization solutions adopted by other relevant projects in the domain of Social Sciences and Humanities: CENDARI, PARTHENOS, and SSHOC.

2.1 CENDARI

The Collaborative European Digital Archival Research Infrastructure (CENDARI) project (funded by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Program), had the objective of establishing a research infrastructure in the humanities that would integrate archive access, knowledge connection, and research support in two specific areas: First World War studies and Medieval History. One of the anticipated outcomes, particularly from the efforts of CENDARI's Work Package 6 (WP6), was the development of a knowledge framework that combined an integrated metadata strategy and dynamic domain ontologies: this is CENDARI's incarnation of a common semantic framework.

CENDARI's framework has been designed to ensure consistency, coherence, and meaningful connections across the various data, metadata, and ontologies employed within the project, with a specific emphasis on the project's domains.

Key elements of the semantic framework implemented by CENDARI include:

- Metadata standards and Schemas
- A dedicated ontology (based on the general-purpose ontology CIDOC-CRM)
- Controlled Vocabularies
- Interoperability/integration layers

Metadata Schemas

The priority for the WP6 team in CENDARI was to create an *institutional level* metadata schema to enable WP5 to commence work on populating CENDARI with archival descriptions. Subsequently, WP6's work on metadata has focused on reviewing and deciding upon the necessary elements for schemas at the *collection* and *item* level. The work was done in close collaboration with domain experts, that are also the final users of the product. The expected results of this approach were: i) interoperability with archive portals; ii) to satisfy the requirements of researchers.

More in detail, the three-level metadata framework developed by the WP6 team utilizes both new and existing schemas to map all the information, as detailed in the table:

Level	Metadata standard
Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encoded Archival Guide (EAG)
Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encoded Archival Description (EAD) • CENDARI Collection Schema (created <i>ad hoc</i>)
Item	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) • Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) • CENDARI Collection Schema (created <i>ad hoc</i>)

The CENDARI Collection Schema (CCS) was created to allow detailed encoding of collection information, addressing gaps, usage impediments, and future plans. The schema i) enriches the MODS metadata schema at the item level, catering to the detailed requirements of medieval research; ii) integrates TEI elements for manuscript descriptions, lacunae and bibliography; iii) overcomes MODS limitations in capturing intricate codicological features. Consistent cataloging rules prevent redundancy and ensure interoperability between MODS and TEI. Simultaneously, customization aligns elements with CENDARI's needs, adapting the EAG standard for accurate representation, offering precise information tailored to project objectives.

The integrated metadata strategy is a part of the broader CENDARI knowledge framework and is designed to integrate with the designed ontologies.

The division in levels is very important within the CENDARI framework since it is also referenced on the ontology, that is divided into three types of semantic schemas, according to the metadata available for each level.

Generally, it is recommended to use the established schemas since they are already broadly used and there isn't the risk of knowledge enclosure. In fact, if the use of a schema remains only inside the project, it can affect the interoperability objective.

Ontology

CENDARI addressed some key points in the definition of its ontology:

- It should act as a unifying framework
- It should enable alignment of different resources
- It should foster discovery of new knowledge
- It should form the base of the data integration strategy

To address these points, it was decided to adopt the CIDOC-CRM ontology, with minor extensions to adapt the schema to the specific domains' needs. In its final version, CENDARI uses six primary classes:

- Places
- Agents
- Timespans
- Events
- Concepts

The ontology played an essential part in CENDARI's data integration strategy. CIDOC-CRM goes beyond simple hierarchies, including rich interconnections between concepts. It enabled the transformation of a static representation of knowledge into a dynamic and queryable database.

Vocabularies

CENDARI defines *controlled vocabularies* as reference tools comprising standardized terminology and expressions employed to denote concepts, tangible attributes, individuals, locations, occurrences, themes, and various other ideas. Used for the classification, indexing, and retrieval of information, controlled vocabularies facilitate organized management of data. A variety of vocabularies is employed, ranging from concise lists tailored to specific attributes (e.g., reasons for lacunae in manuscripts) to extensive ontologies that amalgamate thousands of terms from various sources (e.g., CENDARI's concept ontology, which integrates LCSH and DDC). All of these are integrated with the overall reference ontology based on CIDOC-CRM.

Best practices for interoperability

In the context of CENDARI, interoperability is achieved through a workflow comprised of a few key passages: i) Crosswalks and transformations enable metadata record creation at the collection level using the CENDARI Collection Schema (CCS); ii) Crosswalks between CCS and Encoded Archival Description (EAD) formats facilitate record transformation; iii) XSLT transformations on the CENDARI metadata page generate EAD from CSS-encoded metadata, ensuring interoperability with various systems; iv) Consistent cataloging rules, particularly at the item level, prevent redundancy between MODS and TEI; v) Domain-specific considerations involve close consultation with specialists, tailoring the schema for research needs, and including elements to enhance historical search and discovery. This approach aims to ensure interoperability with online archive portals, meeting specific requirements for researchers in the historical domain.

2.2 PARTHENOS

PARTHENOS (Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies) is a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme with the objective of strengthening the cohesion of research across several related fields associated with the humanities. It is worth mentioning that both DARIAH and CLARIN (two out of the four participating RIs in H2IOOSC) actively participated in the project and thus in the development of its semantic framework. PARTHENOS was committed to establishing common standards, coordinating joint activities, and harmonizing policy implementation while pooling services and sharing solutions to address shared challenges. PARTHENOS worked on interdisciplinary research starting from the digitization of data, actively collaborating with thematic research infrastructures, and contributing to the development of common data standards and online services. Going beyond coordination, PARTHENOS links and harmonizes initiatives to create a unified platform, streamlining researcher access. By pooling and enhancing these solutions, interlinking existing services, and introducing new tools, PARTHENOS effectively brings an example to bridge gaps in the evolving landscape of digital research.

In this context, the common semantic framework is described as a common layer for interoperability of resources coming from different domains that impacts long term integration and sustainability.

The declared challenge to be addressed is: how to create a layer of interoperability between RIs (in this case DARIAH, CLARIN and other EU-level actors) which will offer an information model that will allow the integration of records from highly diverse individual RIs into a common view that a) allows for the exploitation of resources across the participating member RIs in a way that maintains the epistemic validity of those resources and b) create an environment for a sustainable, expanding integration of these resources according to the needs of researchers and RIs. To address these challenges PARTHENOS proposed a framework with the following elements:

- Information Management architecture and process;
- Semantic Model for representing RIs data;
- Minimal metadata proposal for tracking the identity of resources in a common semantic environment.

A registry of resources and their keepers within the environment should also be established.

The common semantic framework should provide support to the implementation of an aggregation service to find all data in one place.

Semantic Model

A semantic framework exploiting an ontological modeling of data structures considered as propositional statements about the world is proposed as the means for creating the data expression which can support an agile framework for the representation and management of cross-RI metadata about resources.

The original data remains the prerogative of the individual research communities. The RIs system objective is to map the data on a common ontology that doesn't substitute the original data; it enriches them with a layer of integration as added value. The use of the ontology provides added value. The aim of the model is accessibility of resources.

The semantic model should be able to represent and connect the process of knowledge generation.

Heterogeneous data must be connected in order to have common ground. The strategy for connecting and linking the various data includes the Vocabulary Management System and the Reference Data Integration Workflow

Vocabulary Management System

A Vocabulary Management System (VMS) aims to address the heterogeneity of data by classifying it. One of the challenges in organizing diverse resources is the establishment of common points of contact, which involve the use of vocabularies and thesauri.

Information architecture

The solution proposed by the PARTHENOS Project in Deliverable 5.1 is to establish a communication center to keep the federation updated about the communities that hold data, since research is a work in motion that is continuously enriched.

Data curation: create a research environment to have a communication cycle where researchers are supported and facilitated in terms of efficiency and clarity (transparency) regarding the management of resources in the common framework => Common Information Space => Architecture proposition: components that allow cross-domain registration and curation inside a centralized information service.

Element	Scope
Registry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transforms metadata from Research Infrastructures - Provides a current snapshot of ongoing curation processes - Utilizes a semantic graph to describe relations - Focuses on minimal metadata for resource identification

Content Layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains both data and metadata about distributed resources mapped from the Registry - Manages all changes to the registry
Indexes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open set of indices generated using the registry for specific retrieval purposes. - Available to users through the query system
Query System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables hybrid research across registry and community-generated indices
Ris Management System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allows supervision, planning, and tracing of workflows and progress in RI maintenance actions

Reference Data Integration Workflow

The chosen ontology is CIDOC-CRM.

Workflow:

- Identification
- Discovery
- Creation
- Registration
- Integration
- Implementation

From the analysis of the work done for PARTHENOS some common issues have emerged throughout the description of the workflow implementation:

- Heterogeneity of data
- Obsolescence of technical solution to store and manage data
- Contribution of domain experts is necessary to have an in-depth knowledge of resources
- To have high level structures to support resources according to the FAIR principles

2.3 SSHOC

The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a project funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 framework program gathering 20 partner organizations and their 27 associates in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Whereas in PARTHENOS 2 out of 4 RIs in the Social and Cultural Innovation (S&CI) ESFRI landscape were participating, in SSHOC 3 out of 4 (including DARIAH, CLARIN and E-RIHS) were actively developing the described solutions, making this experience a very close reference for the H2IOSC activities.

SSHOC provided a semantic interoperability framework for incorporating the varied data pertaining to the SSH disciplinary domains and describing their lifecycle. The main component of the SSHOC semantic framework is a dedicated ontology, SSHOCro, based on CIDOC-CRM. Several specific workflows for data integration and validation were also explored for specific use cases relevant to the SSH community.

Ontology and data model

The SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro) proposes an ontological model and RDF Schema to organize knowledge in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). Developed in the context of

the SSHOC project, SSHOCro complements and extends the CIDOC-CRM ontology, the standard reference ontology in SSH research workflows. SSHOCro aims to provide a semantic interoperability framework for describing the data lifecycle in the SSH disciplinary domains; it emphasizes an event-centric approach, inherited from CIDOC-CRM, for digital provenance models. It enables documenting primary data collection, preliminary and final results, methods, and protocols at each stage of research. The ontology's formalization incorporates provenance metadata, supporting the assessment of meaning, relevance, quality, and possibilities of improvement. SSHOCro facilitates resource discovery, allowing social scientists to publish and share research through data repositories. It serves as a high-level workflow logbook, documenting processes for validation and reuse. The ontology is designed to contribute to a common language for information integration and knowledge networks in cultural heritage and beyond. It acknowledges the diversity of data types and analytical techniques in the social sciences and humanities, emphasizing an iterative research process. SSHOCro's practical use lies in metadata capture schemes for individual projects and mapping, transforming, and integrating data across projects and disciplines, creating interoperable pools of information for reuse.

The development of SSHOCro follows a bottom-up strategy based on actual empirical data and data structures. The ontology focuses on describing research activities in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), their methods, and goals, considering the context in which they occur. The process involved identifying workflow patterns and metadata standards through literature review, workshops, and consultations with SSH data providers.

The ontology development was influenced by extensive research on SSH data repositories, consultation with community members, and consideration of use-cases for validation, so, beside the CIDOC-CRM model it also incorporates information from other ontologies and data models

The model emphasizes the archivist's perspective, focusing on registering information relevant to metadata records, data creation, and availability in a static manner. The goal is not to propose a theory of everything but to model well-understood concepts for data-driven research in SSH.

The development involved identifying high-level generalizations and defining superclasses to maintain simplicity and economy. The ontology was validated through case studies, workshops, and feedback from the SSHOC community.

The ontology relies on existing documented data, with abstractions sought for groups of classes sharing common characteristics. It distinguishes between concepts referring directly to objects/entities and those implying a complex structure mediated by events and relations.

References:

1. D4.18: <https://sshopencloud.eu/d418-sshoc-reference-ontology-beta-version>
2. D4.20: <https://sshopencloud.eu/d420-sshocro-final-version>
3. MS19: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ms19-consultation-ssh-data-producers>

Validation, workflows and tools

The validation process extended to use cases in Heritage Science, Archaeology, and an Open Linked Data Archaeology Case Study. Mappings with other ontologies were performed for alignment.

The workflows proposed in the project are not simple sequences of procedures, with one operation following the other in a linear and predetermined order. Instead, they capture an open process, whereby one can always backtrack to alter bits and pieces of the workflow components, in an iterative manner. This closely reflects the stages involved in information processing in the scientific process - i.e., the iterative, incremental way in which scientific knowledge is produced and verified.

Several SSHOC project deliverables document specific workflows based on relevant use cases which are representative of the data ingestion, validation, and semantization process in general. Furthermore, the project defined an open marketplace that collects individual contributions to the overall project effort, along with a requisite specification that tools must align to in order to be included in the marketplace.

References

1. D4.19: <https://sshopencloud.eu/d419-mapping-two-indicative-selected-standards-sshocro-0>
2. D5.16: <https://sshopencloud.eu/d516-report-making-heritage-science-data-fair-open-data-heritage-science-and-archaeology>
3. D7.1: <https://sshopencloud.eu/d71-system-specification-ssh-open-marketplace>
4. MS20 <https://sshopencloud.eu/ms-20-selection-ssh-metadata-standards-mapping-sshocro>
5. MS49: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/restore> - <https://zenodo.org/records/5217113>

3. INTERRELATION WITH OTHER WPs

The workflow employed by WP4 to finalize the H2IOSC CSF has emphasized a cyclic design, with periodical reviews and upgrades implemented based on novel resources and information acquired in time. This workflow style is essential to maintain an updated and sustainable model and will continue beyond the formal conclusion of the project. While the construction of the CSF is overseen by WP4, the WP activities are strongly connected to the activities of the other H2IOSC WPs. A detailed list of interactions is:

- An observatory on resources (data, services, standards, ontologies...) was created within the WP2 with the support of the company gruppoMETA, which is also responsible of the development of the H2IOSC Marketplace. WP2 provides information about digital resources, standards, community needs, FAIR assessment, access, and all the information about resources and projects the RIs are involved with; the gathered data informed the construction of the CSF.
- WP3 offered technical evaluation on FAIRness and technological requirements assessment of resources to be mapped
- The WP5 and WP6 together have had the strongest impact on the CSF definition, providing not only a comprehensive list of services and tools provided by the federated RIs, but also a standardized framework for their description (powered by machine-readable *manifests* developed as part of WP6) and inclusion in and orchestration by the H2IOSC Marketplace which is the main output of WP5
- The CSF provides the common layer for interoperability to the pilots developed in WP7
- The diffusion of the CSF will lead to the emergence of training needs for researcher to be addressed in WP8

4. THE COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK IN H2IOSC

The final version of the CSF in the H2IOSC project ultimately emerged “on the field”, from strong and positive interaction and discussion among the 4 participating RIs and from the practical needs of their reference communities and the technical necessities of their respective software platforms, all of which are new implementations whose realization was facilitated by H2IOSC. The positive output of

the discussion carried out during the project can be seen in the collaborative effort which brought about the definition of the “Manuscript Ontology”, which saw the participation of all RIs, each contributing a part of the ontology: CLARIN focused on linguistic aspects, DARIAH elaborated on the philological methodology, E-RIHS brought the physical dimension of the objects in the discussion and OPERAS took care of digital editions. The result of this work is well described by Deliverable 4.13, which is the interim version of the current final deliverable. However, it is to be stressed that here “final” simply means “at the current moment”; the information outlined in this document should not be seen as a definitive statement, but rather as a living standard which is expected to continue evolving during the lifecycle of the H2IOSC federation, which goes far beyond the end of the project. Further details can be found in section 6. STRATEGY FOR UPDATING AND FINAL RELEASE OF DELIVERABLE D4.14.

The CSF consists of several components:

- An Architectural Mapping formal description listing the platforms, services, data repositories and other tools contributed by each RI; in particular, this includes a continuously updated Catalogue of Services
- A comprehensive list of all data types that can be expected to be dealt with during the project's lifetime
- The H2IOSC data and integration model, developed mainly by WP6 and extensively used in the project's Marketplace (WP5)
- A workflow for the maintenance and constant updating of the CSF itself
- A set of vertical ontologies, taxonomies, and controlled vocabularies used by the individual RIs and by individual tools for more detailed and context-specific description of resources

4.1 LIST OF DATATYPES

This is a comprehensive list of the data formats managed in H2IOSC (also listed in the project's Data Management Plan). As for all aspects involving the CSF, the list should not be seen as a static, permanent list but rather as a living specification continuously updated during the lifecycle of the H2IOSC federation, of which the version reported here is just a snapshot.

Category	Formats / Standards
Documents	PDF, DOCX, TXT, HTML, XML
Textual / Archival	TEI, EAD, EAC, EAG, ISBD, ISAD, ISAAR, ISDF, ISDIAH, RIC-CM
Bibliographic	UNIMARC, MARC21, Dublin Core, DataCite
Cultural Heritage	ICCD (Italy), CAT-SAN, METS-SAN
Structured / Semantic	RDF, TTL, NT, NQ, JSON, JSON-LD
3D / Architectural	IFC4, RVT (Revit)
Geospatial	GeoTIFF
Multimedia	TIFF, JPG, PNG, SVG (images), MP3/WAV (audio), MP4/MOV/MKV (video)

4.2 ARCHITECTURAL MAPPING

A detailed schema of the architectural components, comprising all the platforms, datasets, services and tools managed by each RI, is maintained as part of the project's services. A snapshot detailing the architectural overview, as of the composition of the present document, is reported below. Once again,

it must be kept in mind that the architectural schema is a living specification, subject to constant maintenance during the federation’s lifetime.

MODULE	CLARIN			
Resources Discovery	CLARIN National Repositories	CLARIN.it FCS endpoint (FCS)	CLARIN.it Harvesting (VLO)	CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard
Services provision	CLARIN.it Servizi Linguistici	CLARIN.it Servizio di Deposito	CLARIN.it FAIRification service	
Services provision & discovery	CLARIN LRS	CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard		
Data lake (metadata)	CLARIN National Repositories	CLARIN.it Training Platform		
AAI / SSO	CLARIN AAI SSO			
Data Store (resources)	CLARIN.it ILC 4 CLARIN (DSpace)	CLARIN.it Training Library	CLARIN.it Training Platform	CLARIN.it Datacenter
Pilots	CLARIN.it Pilot #1	CLARIN.it Pilot #2	CLARIN.it Pilot #3	
API Management	CLARIN.it WSO2 API Manager			
Services composition	CLARIN WSO2 Micro Integrator			
	DARIAH			
Resources Discovery	DARIAH.it MKT	DARIAH.it METAFAIR Ecosystem	DARIAH.it DPH census of witnesses	
Services provision	DARIAH.it AEON (Runtime)	DARIAH.it DPH multiple components		
Services provision & discovery	DARIAH.it AEON, Service catalog			
Data lake (metadata)	DARIAH.it MFE	DARIAH.it MKT		
AAI / SSO	DARIAH AAI (Nanotec)			
Data Store (resources)	DARIAH.it MFE			
Pilots	DARIAH.it DPH	DARIAH.it DMHH		
API Management	DARIAH.it AEON (DIRECTOR)			
Services composition	DARIAH.it AEON (CONNECTOR)			
	E-RIHS			
Resources Discovery	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS DATA Catalog		
Services provision	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS HDIS		
Services provision & discovery	E-RIHS API Gateway			
Data lake (metadata)	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS Data Catalog		
AAI / SSO	E-RIHS IDENTITY SERVER DIGILAB	E-RIHS IDENTITY SERVER H2IOSC (Nanotec)		
Data Store (resources)	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS Data Store		
Pilots	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS Pilot WebApp (Illuminated mss)		
API Management	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS HDIS		
Services composition	E-RIHS API Gateway	E-RIHS C-VRE		
	OPERAS			
Resources Discovery	OPERAS MKT			
Services provision	OPERAS MKT			
Services provision & discovery	OPERAS MKT			
Data lake (metadata)	OPERAS MKT Deposit Area			
AAI / SSO	OPERAS Identity Server			
Data Store (resources)	OPERAS MKT			
Pilots	OPERAS FAIRification service	OPERAS digital edition of printed texts		
API Management	OPERAS WSO2 API Manager			
Services composition	OPERAS WSO2 Micro Integrator			

4.3 DATA/INTEGRATION MODEL

An essential element of the H2IOSC platform architecture is the mandatory, formal description of all shared via machine-readable *manifests*. The format of these manifests was established as part of WP6, which also includes facilities for the assisted production of standard-compliant manifests for newly added resources. The manifests will complement each service and offer a standardized description of each service which includes metadata, identifier comprised, input/output parameters, endpoints, OpenAPI definitions, and the level of technological, social, legal, and organizational maturity. The manifest thus acts as a descriptive interface between the service provider and the federation and is specifically used to allow inclusion of the service in H2IOSC’s Marketplace, providing a bridge between the local development environment and the project’s orchestration system. The exposure of the manifest allows for the immediate and automated registration and publication of the service within the Marketplace and defines its compatibility with the platform’s data model, ensuring that each described element can be understood and managed by the orchestration system.

The systematic adoption of these manifests essentially simplifies the onboarding of new services, improves the automation of orchestration operations, and promotes system scalability, allowing for standardization of the way services are exposed and consumed. This approach ensures greater interoperability between different infrastructures and enables the implementation of a modular and extensible orchestration model. The detailed description of the manifest model is demanded to the relevant WP6 deliverables. A short example is included below:

```
{
  "service": {
    "name": "Example Service",
    "openapi_url": "http://anyurl.org/openapi/v1/example-service.yaml",
    "policies": {
      "rate_limit": "500rpm",
      "throttling": "burst=5",
      "access_level": "OAuth2"
    }
  }
}
```

4.4 MAINTENANCE AND CONSTANT UPDATING

During the project's lifecycle, a dedicated task group will monitor the CSF specifications, their alignment to FAIR principles, and their adequacy in describing shared resources provided by the RIs. The group will meet periodically and keep the technical specifications comprising the CSF up to date; this will be a natural extension of the continuous integration work which brought to the creation of the CSF in the first place and will be instrumental in keeping the federation alignment to FAIR standard and continued, powerful resource sharing. An example of a possible structure for the control group is provided below, solely for the purpose of illustrating the strategy that the cluster will need to develop.

Charter – CSF Maintenance & Editorial Board

Mission: To ensure semantic coherence, quality assurance, and sustainable evolution of the H2IOSC CSF.

Composition:

- One representative per RI partner (CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, E-RIHS);
- One representative from WP4 (RIs Nodes Resources Interoperability);
- One representative from WP2 (H2IOSC Observatory);
- One representative from WP5 (Marketplace);
- One representative from WP6 (Semantic Services).

Core responsibilities:

- Manage versioning of the CSF, manifests, and vertical ontologies;
- Validate proposed extensions through an internal RFC process;
- Monitor FAIR KPIs and maintain Quality Gates for onboarding;
- Publish guidance and best practice documentation;
- Oversee technical maintenance of the CSF Registry and namespaces;
- Facilitate coordination across Work Packages to ensure alignment between semantic, technical, and infrastructural developments.

Release cycle:

- Major release every 12 months
- Minor release every 6 months
- Patch/hotfix on demand

Change management:

All changes are logged into a public Change Log. Deprecated versions remain accessible for at least 24 months.

4.5 FEDERATION PILOT: APPLIED INTEROPERABILITY STRATEGIES IN WP4

As part of the cluster's broader strategic vision, the Federation Pilot has been conceived as an external objective complementary to the formal scope of the project. Although not explicitly included in the Grant Agreement, it plays a key role in demonstrating the operational maturity of the interoperability strategies developed under WP4 and in preparing their long-term sustainability beyond the project's lifetime.

The Federation Pilot operationalizes the Common Semantic Framework (CSF) by linking multiple Research Infrastructures (RIs) through federated workflows, harmonized APIs, and shared AAI protocols. Building on the CSF's FAIR/CARE-compliant architecture, it establishes a distributed ecosystem in which data, metadata, and services from the four participating RIs—DARIAH, CLARIN, OPERAS, and E-RIHS—can be accessed and orchestrated transparently across nodes.

The Pilot concretely illustrates how WP4's interoperability principles—semantic alignment, technical standardization, and federated governance—are jointly implemented. Using WSO2 API Manager for gateway orchestration, Keycloak-based AAI integration, and JSON/OpenAPI manifests for service description, it demonstrates a fully traceable and machine-actionable interoperability layer. The validation phase—covering end-to-end connectivity, latency, and security testing—confirms the robustness and scalability of the approach, while its publication on the H2IOSC Marketplace provides a reusable model for future inter-IR integrations and for the progressive expansion of the federation.

In practical terms, the Federation Pilot represents the proof of concept of WP4's design philosophy: an evolving, self-validating federation capable of maintaining long-term alignment with FAIR and EOSC principles through continuous monitoring and controlled updating of the CSF specifications, as outlined in Section 4.4. It also anticipates the post-project maintenance framework, demonstrating how the CSF and its derived implementations can continue to evolve under the governance mechanisms defined by the cluster.

4.6 DOMAIN-SPECIFIC ONTOLOGIES

Finally, each of the 4 participating RIs will keep an internal specification of the ontologies, vocabularies and datatypes which may be needed to manage domain-specific resources and are not already included in the common framework. Detailed description of these additional ontologies is out of scope of the present document and is delegated to the technical documentation of each RI's platform. It is intended that any shared resources and service interaction must be aligned with the CSF to be managed properly, and the onus of alignment is on the RI providing the new resource type.

4.7 ONTOLOGICAL DECISION AND H2IOSC-CSF PROFILE

The CSF of H2IOSC adopts, as its common modelling baseline:

- CIDOC-CRM (ISO 21127) as the core ontology for the representation of cultural heritage entities, events, and contextual relations;
- SSHOCro (Research Object Ontology) for the formalization of research processes, datasets, and services;
- Secondary references: DCAT-AP, PROV-O, FOAF, SKOS, and OntoLex-Lemon for lexical and vocabulary representation.

All domain-specific ontologies developed by the Research Infrastructures (RIs) must be mapped to or extended from the H2IOSC-CSF Profile according to the following rules:

- Every new class or property must have a super-class within the CSF Profile.
- The extension must include a SHACL shape documenting its constraints and validation rules.
- Each new ontology is submitted to the CSF Registry and undergoes an acceptance review to certify semantic compatibility.

The profile will be published, versioned and dereferenceable in the technical sections of the H2IOSC website

5. CONCLUSIONS

The primary objective of H2IOSC's CSF is to enhance the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of shared data, tools, and resources within the project. This goal is achieved through the implementation of mapping and modeling strategies. The framework also incorporates the management of thesauri and vocabularies associated with various disciplinary domains.

The framework provides comprehensive guidelines for essential processes such as data assessment, semantization, homogenization, transformation, and validation. These guidelines have been continuously updated and improved throughout the project and will continue to be upgraded after the project's conclusion. To ensure compatibility and facilitate resource integration, a set of standardized vocabularies and mapping schemas have been selected, compatibly with the diverse array of platforms and services provided by the participating RIs. This approach not only enhances the project's sustainability but also enables the reuse of mapping schemas for resources adhering to compatible standards while accommodating new resources that bring with them different standards. By employing these strategies, the CSF serves as a crucial tool in promoting effective data management and facilitating collaboration within the project.

The H2IOSC project has leveraged the knowledge gained from previous initiatives such as CENDARI, PARTHENOS, and SSHOC to establish a robust Common Semantic Framework. These projects have played a crucial role in identifying essential components for constructing a solid framework, which include the definition of reference ontology, standardized vocabularies, and a practical workflow for integrating data. The experiences and methodologies provided by these projects have proven invaluable, serving as a strong basis for the ongoing activities within the H2IOSC project.

Taking a forward-looking perspective, WP4 has established, and will continue to upgrade, a sustainable workflow for integrating resources from various RIs. This workflow aims to ensure adaptability in the face of evolving standards and the changing needs of the research community. Drawing upon prior experiences and actively involving domain experts, WP4 endeavors to overcome challenges associated with data heterogeneity, technological obsolescence, and compliance with established standards.

By orchestrating concerted efforts and fostering collaboration among Research Infrastructure and their reference communities, the H2IOSC project strives to create a robust and enduring framework for collaboration within the broad fields of the humanities and heritage sciences. This framework is powered by systematic, standardized sharing of data, services and resources in general, and will enhance capabilities and foster cooperation among researchers and research institutions. Through these collective endeavors, the project's final aim is to facilitate knowledge exchange, advance research methodologies, and contribute to the progress of the respective fields.

6. FINAL RELEASE OF D4.14 AND STRATEGY FOR CONSTANT UPDATING

The goal is to deliver, by the end of the project (April 2026), a final and consolidated version of Deliverable D4.14 representing a fully operational Common Semantic Framework (CSF).

The final release of D4.14 will consolidate the specifications, ontologies, and manifest models developed during the H2IOSC lifecycle into a coherent and interoperable framework supporting all federation services, including the Federation Pilot, which serves as the primary proof of concept for testing and validating the CSF's interoperability mechanisms across RIs. The Pilot thus provides the operational evidence base for the framework's maturity and readiness for adoption at scale.

After the project's conclusion, the CSF and its dependent implementations—such as the Pilot and related semantic registries—will be maintained and further evolved by the federation under the governance strategy defined by the cluster. As described in Section 4.4, a dedicated CSF Maintenance & Editorial Board will oversee this process to ensure semantic coherence, continuous alignment to FAIR principles, and the sustainable evolution of the framework.

This Board, composed of representatives from all RIs (CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, E-RIHS) and from relevant Work Packages (WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6), will manage versioning cycles, validate proposed extensions through an internal RFC process, and maintain quality assurance via FAIR KPIs and onboarding gates. The framework will adopt a structured release policy—major releases every 12 months, minor updates every 6 months, and on-demand hotfixes—ensuring transparency through a public change log. Deprecated versions will remain accessible for a minimum of 24 months to guarantee traceability and reproducibility.

Through this continuous maintenance strategy, the CSF will remain a living, evolving framework—technically robust, semantically consistent, and capable of supporting long-term interoperability within the H2IOSC federation and the broader EOSC ecosystem.

REFERENCES

1. Deliverable developed by the CENDARI WP6 team. «CENDARI D6.3 Guidelines for Ontology Building». July 2014.
<http://www.cendari.eu/sites/default/files/CENDARI%20D6.3%20Guidelines%20for%20Ontology%20Building.pdf>
2. Bruseker, George, Martin Doerr, e Maria Theodoridou. «PARTHENOS D5.1 Report on the Common Semantic Framework». Zenodo, 30 aprile 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2668433>.
3. Bruseker, George, Alessia Bardi, Felix Helfer, Eleni Tsoulouha, Elias Tzortzakakis, e Ksenia Zaytseva. «PARTHENOS D5.7 Report on the Integration of Reference Resources». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2671619>.
4. Bekiari, Chrysoula, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «SSHOC D4.18 SSHOC Reference Ontology (beta Version)». Zenodo, 26 marzo 2020.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3744861>.
5. Chrysoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS19 Consultation with SSH Data Producers». Zenodo, 30 giugno 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5914407>.
6. Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Chrysoula Bekiari, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.19 Mapping of Two Indicative Selected Standards to the Sshocro». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4457496>.
7. Chrysoula Bekiari, Athina Kritsotaki, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.20 Sshocro (final Version)». Zenodo, 27 aprile 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6771757>.
8. Joseph Padfield, Orla Delaney, e Anna Amat Alberti. «D5.16 Report on Making Heritage Science Data FAIR (open Data in Heritage Science and Archaeology)». Zenodo, 30 aprile 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6779595>.
9. Laure Barbot, Yoan Moranville, Frank Fischer, Clara Petitfils, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Tomasz Parkoła, Philipp Wieder, e Sotiris Karampatakis. «SSHOC D7.1 System Specification - SSH Open Marketplace». Zenodo, 19 novembre 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558302>.
10. Chrysoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Maurizio Sanesi, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS 20 Selection of SSH Metadata Standards for Mapping to Sshocro». Zenodo, 24 giugno 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4582018>.
11. Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, Elisa Brunoni, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot Alpha Release». Zenodo, 31 marzo 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5217113>.